

2nd Global Summit on MATERIALS SCIENCE AND NANOSCIENCE

MATERIALS2026

Dates
July 20-21, 2026

Venue
Prague, Czech Republic

For More Info: <https://materials2026.researchconnects.org/>
Register Now: <https://materials2026.researchconnects.org/registration>

Day-1 | July 20, 2026

09:00 - 09:30

On Spot Registrations

Conference Chair

Rina Tannenbaum, Stony Brook University, USA

Conference Co-Chair

Will be updated soon

P 09:30-10:10

Maria Manuela Silva

University of Minho, Portugal

Title: Energy Materials: Performance and Sustainable Innovation

P 10:10-10:50

Sharath Sriram

Co-Leader-Functional Materials and Microsystems, Australia

Title: Semiconducting Materials Applied to Precision Biosensing

10:50 - 11:05

Refreshment Break

P 11:05-11:45

Horng-Yi Chang

National Taiwan Ocean University, Taiwan

Title: Strontium-based perovskite anodes for hydrogen- and ammonia-fueled solid oxide fuel cells

P 11:45-12:25

Rina Tannenbaum

Stony Brook University, USA

Title: Will be updated soon

P 12:25-13:05

Jiang Yang

Liaoning Petrochemical University, China

Title: Lignin-Derivatives for Dispersing Phthalocyanine Nano-pigments and Enhancing Oil Recovery

13:05 - 14:05

Group Photo / Lunch Break

K 14:05-14:35

Zhexu Xi

University of Oxford, United Kingdom

Title: Rational Design and Functional Optimization of Targeted Magnetic Nanoparticle-based Microfluidic Immuno-capturing Platform

K 14:35-15:05

Pasqualina Liana Scognamiglio

University of Basilicata, Italy

Title: Exploring Bioinspired Materials for Biomedical Applications

K 15:05-15:35

Alisha Miller

University of Birmingham, United Kingdom

Title: Hydropol™: An Innovative Packaging Solution to Combat the Microplastic Monster

15:35 - 15:50

Refreshment Break

K 15:50-16:20

Tamar N. Bzhalava

Georgian Technical University, Georgia

Title: Nanoscale Materials: Optical Properties, Computational Modelling, Application in Biomedicine

K 16:20-16:50

Ramesh S. Chaughule

Ramnarain Ruia Autonomous College, India

Title: Sustainable Bioengineered Nano materials for Healthcare and Packaging Applications

Sessions

Computational Materials Science & Materials Design, Optical, Electronic & Functional Materials, Nanomaterials Synthesis & Processing

Session Chair

Navid Alinejadian, University of Twente, Netherlands

I 16:50-17:15

Baris Cetin & Caner Bakrac

FNSS Savunma Sistemleri, Turkey

Title: A Computational Based Framework Strategy on Driveline System Components Design at FNSS

I 17:15-17:40

Muhammad Saad

University of Freiburg, Germany

Title: Interfacial Mechanics of CVD Graphene: How Copper Crystal Orientation Dictates Adhesion Energy

I 17:40-18:05

Slot Available

I 18:05-18:30

F. Selen Gunden

Ege University, Turkey

Title: Development of High-Sensitivity Electrochemical Biosensors Using Electrodes Fabricated with 3D Printing Technology

POSTER-01

Keon-Soo Jang

University of Suwon, South Korea

Title: Will be updated soon

POSTER-02

Ilia chachava

Georgia petre melikishvi research institute, Georgia

Title: Kinetic Regularities Of Oligomer Formation In Melamine-Formaldehyde And Carbamide-Melamine-Formaldehyde Systems

Closing the Conference for Day 1

Day-2 | July 21, 2026

Conference Chair

Rina Tannenbaum, Stony Brook University, USA

Conference Co-Chair

Will be updated soon

P 09:30-10:10

Navid Alinejadian

University of Twente, Netherlands

Title: Will be updated soon

P 10:10-10:50

Pelagia-Irene Gouma

The Ohio State University, USA

Title: Advanced Manufacturing of Ceramic Materials

10:50 - 11:05

Refreshment Break

P 11:05-11:45

Sharmila M. Mukhopadhyay

University of Maine, USA

Title: Hierarchical Hybrid Superstructures for Precisely Tailored Multifunctional Properties

P 11:45-12:25

Haixue Yan

Queen Mary University of London, United Kingdom

Title: Characterization of Ferroelectric Polarization Switching at Different Frequencies

P 13:05-11:45

Slot Available

13:05 - 14:05

Group Photo / Lunch Break

K 14:05-14:45

Mounim Lebrini

University of Antilles, France

Title: Plant-Derived Alkaloids as Sustainable Corrosion Inhibitors for Metal Alloys: A Mechanistic and Experimental Study

K 14:45-15:15

Valeri Barsegov

University of Massachusetts, USA

Title: Dynamic Force Spectroscopy in Silico: Exploring Strength, Deformability, Toughness and Mechanical Fatigue of Biological Nanoparticles

K 15:15-15:45

Auchynnikaŭ Y. V

Yanka Kupala State University of Grodno, Belarus

Title: Nanocomposite Vacuum Coatings Based on Altins

15:45 - 16:00

Refreshment Break

K 16:00-16:25

Mounim Lebrini

University of Antilles, France

Title: Plant-Derived Alkaloids as Sustainable Corrosion Inhibitors for Metal Alloys: A Mechanistic and Experimental Study

K 16:25-16:50

Slot Available

Sessions

Computational Materials Science & Materials Design, Optical, Electronic & Functional Materials, Nanomaterials Synthesis & Processing, Surface Engineering, Coatings & Tribology

Session Chair

Will be updated soon

I 16:50-17:15

Rodriguez Rocio

University of Alicante, Spain

Title: Will be updated soon

I 17:15-17:40

Snezana Pantovic

University of Montenegro, Montenegro

Title: Integrated Bioactive and Blood-Derived Biomaterials: Translational Interfaces in Regenerative and Clinical Medicine

I 17:40-18:05

Bhawna Sharma

Chemnitz University of Technology, Germany

Title: Optimization of Recycling Processes for Biodegradable Bioplastics: a Structure-Property Relationships Approach

I 18:05-18:30

Vimala Sridurai

University of Manchester, UK

Title: Will be updated soon

I 18:30-18:55

Slot Available

POSTER-03

Riva liparteliani

Georgia petre melikishvi research institute, Georgia

Title: Seed Pelleting And Encapsulation Using Biodegradable Amide-Aldehyde Oligomers For Improved Wheat Germination

POSTER-04

Ia chitrekashvili

Georgia petre melikishvi research institute, Georgia

Title: Biodegradable Polymeric Controlled-Release Nitrogen Fertilizers: Synthesis, Structure Regulation And Environmental Compatibility

Closing the Conference

